

Exact Solution of Navier-Stokes Equations

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Abstract: In Navier-Stokes equations (NASA's Navier-Stokes Equations, 3-dimensional-unsteady), we discover the exact solution by Newton potential function and time-function. We think the solution likely Newton potential function that be able to solve Laplace equation.

Keywords: Navier-Stokes Equations; Exact solutions; Newton potential function; Time function

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1. INTRODUCTION

We discover the exact solution in Navier-Stokes equation by Newton potential function and time function.

According NASA's Navier-Stokes Equations (3-dimensional-unsteady),

Coordinate: (x, y, z) , Time: t , Pressure: p , Heat Flux: q

Density: ρ , Stress: τ , Reynolds Number: R_e ,

Velocity Components: (u, v, w) Total Energy: E_t Plandtl Number: P_r

$$\text{Continuity: } \frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho w)}{\partial z} = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{X-Momentum: } & \frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u^2)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho uv)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho uw)}{\partial z} \\ & = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Y-Momentum: } & \frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho uv)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v^2)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho vw)}{\partial z} \\ & = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Z-Momentum: } & \frac{\partial(\rho w)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho uw)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho vw)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho w^2)}{\partial z} \\ & = -\frac{\partial p}{\partial z} + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{yz}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{zz}}{\partial z} \right] \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Energy: } \frac{\partial E_t}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(E_t u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(E_t v)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(E_t w)}{\partial z} = & -\frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial(\rho w)}{\partial z} \\ & - \frac{1}{R_e P_r} \left[\frac{\partial q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial q_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial q_z}{\partial z} \right] \\ & + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (u\tau_{xx} + v\tau_{xy} + w\tau_{xz}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (u\tau_{xy} + v\tau_{yy} + w\tau_{yz}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (u\tau_{xz} + v\tau_{yz} + w\tau_{zz}) \right] \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

2. EXACT SOLUTION IN 3-DIMENSIONAL NAVIER-STOKES EQUATION (INCLUDE TIME)

For we solve equations, we use Newton potential function and time function. If we think the solution of Laplace equation,

$$\begin{aligned} u = \frac{C_1}{r^3} x f(t), v = \frac{C_1}{r^3} y f(t), w = \frac{C_1}{r^3} z f(t), r = \sqrt{x^2 + y^2 + z^2} \\ \rho = \rho_0, r > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

In this case, we solve Eq(1).

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho w)}{\partial z} = f(t)\rho_0 \left[-\frac{3C_1}{r^5} (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) + \frac{3C_1}{r^3} \right] = 0 \quad (7)$$

Second point, in Eq(2)

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{xx} = \frac{C_2}{r^6} x^2 [f(t)]', \tau_{xy} = \frac{C_2}{r^6} xy [f(t)]', \tau_{xz} = \frac{C_2}{r^6} xz [f(t)]', \\ \dots, \tau_{ij} = \frac{C_2}{r^6} x^i x^j [f(t)]', r > 0 \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(\rho u^2)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(\rho uv)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(\rho uw)}{\partial z} \\ = \rho_0 \dot{f}(t) \frac{C_1}{r^3} x + [f(t)]' \rho_0 \left[-\frac{6C_1^2}{r^8} (x^3 + xy^2 + xz^2) + \frac{C_1^2}{r^6} (2x + x + x) \right] \\ = \rho_0 \dot{f}(t) \frac{C_1}{r^3} x - [f(t)]' \rho_0 \frac{2C_1^2}{r^6} x \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

In this time, if $f(t)$ is,

$$\frac{1}{[f(t)]'} \frac{d}{dt} [f(t)] = 1 \rightarrow f(t) = \frac{1}{C'-t}, t \geq 0, C' < 0 \text{ is constant} \quad (10)$$

Therefore,

$$\begin{aligned} = \rho_0 \frac{1}{(C'-t)^2} \frac{C_1}{r^3} x - \frac{1}{(C'-t)^2} \rho_0 \frac{2C_1^2}{r^6} x \\ = -\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial \tau_{xx}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xy}}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial \tau_{xz}}{\partial z} \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{R_e} \left[-\frac{6C_2}{r^8} (x^3 + xy^2 + xz^2) + \frac{C_2}{r^6} (2x + x + x) \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2} \\
 &= -\frac{\partial p}{\partial x} - \frac{1}{R_e} \frac{2C_2}{r^6} x \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

Hence, in Eq(2), in Eq(3) and in Eq(4),

$$\begin{aligned}
 \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} &= \left[\frac{2x}{r^6} (\rho_0 C_1^2 - \frac{C_2}{R_e}) - \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r^3} x \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2} = \left[\frac{2C_3}{r^6} x - \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r^3} x \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2}, \\
 \frac{\partial p}{\partial y} &= \left[\frac{2y}{r^6} (\rho_0 C_1^2 - \frac{C_2}{R_e}) - \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r^3} y \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2} = \left[\frac{2C_3}{r^6} y - \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r^3} y \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2}, \\
 \frac{\partial p}{\partial z} &= \left[\frac{2z}{r^6} (\rho_0 C_1^2 - \frac{C_2}{R_e}) - \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r^3} z \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2} = \left[\frac{2C_3}{r^6} z - \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r^3} z \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2} C_3 = \rho_0 C_1^2 - \frac{C_2}{R_e}
 \end{aligned} \tag{12}$$

Therefore,

$$p = \left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{C_3}{r^4} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r} \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2}, \quad C_3 = \rho_0 C_1^2 - \frac{C_2}{R_e}, \quad r > 0 \tag{13}$$

In Eq(5), if E_t, q_i is,

$$E_t = E_0, \quad q_x = \frac{C_4}{r^4} \frac{x}{(C_1 - t)^3}, \quad q_y = \frac{C_4}{r^4} y \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3}, \quad q_z = \frac{C_4}{r^4} z \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3}, \quad r > 0 \tag{14}$$

$$\frac{\partial E_t}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial(E_t u)}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial(E_t v)}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial(E_t w)}{\partial z} = 0 \tag{15}$$

As,

$$(\rho u, \rho v, \rho w) = \left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{C_3 C_1}{r^7} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^4} \right] (x, y, z) \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3}, \quad r > 0 \tag{16}$$

Hence,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &-\frac{\partial(\rho u)}{\partial x} - \frac{\partial(\rho v)}{\partial y} - \frac{\partial(\rho w)}{\partial z} \\
 &= \left[\left\{ -7 \frac{C_3 C_1}{2r^9} (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) + 3 \frac{C_3 C_1}{2r^7} \right\} + \left\{ 4\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^6} (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) - 3\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^4} \right\} \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3} \\
 &= \left[-\frac{2C_3 C_1}{r^7} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^4} \right] \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{17}$$

So,

$$\begin{aligned}
 &-\frac{1}{R_e P_r} \left[\frac{\partial q_x}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial q_y}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial q_z}{\partial z} \right] \\
 &= -\frac{1}{R_e P_r} \left[\left\{ -\frac{4C_4}{r^6} (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) + \frac{3C_4}{r^4} \right\} \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3} \right] = \frac{1}{R_e P_r} \frac{C_4}{r^4} \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^3}
 \end{aligned} \tag{18}$$

In this time,

$$\begin{aligned} \tau_{ij} &= \frac{C_2}{r^6} x^i x^j [f(t)]^2 = \frac{C_2}{r^6} x^i x^j \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^2}, r > 0 \\ (\tau_x u, \tau_y v, \tau_z w) &= \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^9} (x^2, y^2, z^2) x^j \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3}, r > 0, t \geq 0, C^1 < 0 \text{ is constant} \\ \frac{1}{R_e} \left[\frac{\partial}{\partial x} (u \tau_{xx} + v \tau_{xy} + w \tau_{xz}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial y} (u \tau_{xy} + v \tau_{yy} + w \tau_{yz}) + \frac{\partial}{\partial z} (u \tau_{xz} + v \tau_{yz} + w \tau_{zz}) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{R_e} \left[-9 \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^{11}} x^2 (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) + \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^9} (3x^2 + y^2 + z^2) \right. \\ &\quad - 9 \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^{11}} y^2 (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) + \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^9} (x^2 + 3y^2 + z^2) \\ &\quad \left. - 9 \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^{11}} z^2 (x^2 + y^2 + z^2) + \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^9} (x^2 + y^2 + 3z^2) \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} \\ &= \frac{1}{R_e} \left[-9 \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^7} + 5 \frac{C_1 C_2}{r^7} \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} = -\frac{1}{R_e} \frac{4C_1 C_2}{r^7} \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} \end{aligned} \tag{19}$$

Hence, Eq(5) is

$$\begin{aligned} 0 &= \left[(-2 \frac{C_1 C_3}{r^7} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^4}) + \frac{1}{R_e P_r} \frac{C_4}{r^4} - \frac{1}{R_e} \frac{4C_1 C_2}{r^7} \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3}, \\ C_3 &= -\frac{2C_2}{R_e} \quad C_4 = -\rho_0 C_1^2 R_e P_r \\ C_3 &= \rho_0 C_1^2 - \frac{C_2}{R_e} = -\frac{2C_2}{R_e}, \quad C_2 = -\rho_0 R_e C_1^2 \end{aligned} \tag{20}$$

Therefore, P is

$$\rho = \left[-\frac{1}{2} \frac{C_3}{r^4} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r} \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^2} = \left[\frac{C_2}{R_e} \frac{1}{r^4} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r} \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^2} = \left[-\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^4} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r} \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^2} \tag{21}$$

$$\begin{aligned} C_4 &= -\rho_0 C_1^2 R_e P_r, \quad q_x = \frac{C_4}{r^4} x \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} = -\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2 R_e P_r}{r^4} \frac{x}{(C^1-t)^3} \\ q_y &= \frac{C_4}{r^4} y \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} = -\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2 R_e P_r}{r^4} y \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} \quad q_z = \frac{C_4}{r^4} z \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} = -\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2 R_e P_r}{r^4} z \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^3} \\ r &> 0, C^1 < 0, t \geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{22}$$

3. CONCLUSION

Therefore, the exact solution of Navier-Stokes equations (3-dimensional-unsteady) is

$$\text{Pressure: } \rho = \left[-\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2}{r^4} + \rho_0 \frac{C_1}{r} \right] \frac{1}{(C^1-t)^2}, \quad r > 0, C^1 < 0, t \geq 0$$

Heat Flux:

$$q_x = -\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2 R_e P_r}{r^4} \frac{x}{(C_1 - t)^3}, q_y = -\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2 R_e P_r}{r^4} \frac{y}{(C_1 - t)^3}, q_z = -\rho_0 \frac{C_1^2 R_e P_r}{r^4} \frac{z}{(C_1 - t)^3}$$

$$r > 0, C_1 < 0, t \geq 0$$

Density: $\rho = \rho_0$,

$$\text{Stress: } \tau_{ij} = \frac{C_2}{r^6} x^i x^j \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2} = -\rho_0 \frac{R_e}{r^6} C_1^2 x^i x^j \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)^2}, r > 0, C_1 < 0, t \geq 0$$

Reynolds Number: R_e , Prandtl Number: P_r

$$\text{Velocity Components: } (u, v, w) = \frac{C_1}{r^3} (x, y, z) \frac{1}{(C_1 - t)}, r > 0, C_1 < 0, t \geq 0$$

Total Energy: $E_t = E_0$

REFERENCES

- [1] Three-dimensional unsteady form of the Navier-Stokes equations: Glenn Research Center, NASA
- [2] D.Yi, Ya. Sinaj, Blow ups of complex solutions of the 3-d-Navier-Stokes system and renormalization group method, J. Eur. Math. Soc **10** (2008), no. 2. 267-313
- [3] I.Gallagher, M. Paicu, Remarks on the blow-up of solutions to a toy model for the Navier-Stokes equations, Proc. Amer. Math. Soc. **17** (2009), no. 6, 2075-3083
- [4] N. H.Katz, A. Tapai, A note on the slightly supercritical Navier-Stokes equations in the plane, preprint
- [5] S. Albeverio, A.B. Cruzeiro, Global flow and invariant (Gibbs) measures for Euler and Navier-Stokes two dimensional fluid. Commun. Math. Phys. **129**, 431-444(1990)
- [6] A. Bensoussan, R. Temman, Equations stochastiques du type Navier-Stokes. J. Funct. Anal. **13**, 195-222(1973)

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